

PROTECTION OF LABOR AND SAFETY IN THE FIELD OF ARCHAEOLOGY

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Annotatsiya. Arxeologik tadqiqotlar ko'plab kasbiy xavflarni, jumladan, jismoniy, biologik va iqlim tahdidlarini o'z ichiga oladi. Maqola arxeologiya sohasida mehnatni muhofaza qilish xususiyatlarini tahlil qilish, potensial xavflarni aniqlash, shuningdek, arxeologik ekspeditsiyalar xodimlarining xavfsizligini ta'minlash bo'yicha tavsiyalar ishlab chiqishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: mehnat muhofazasi, texnika xavfsizligi, ishlab chiqarish, arxeologiya, ekspeditsiya, xavf-xatar, dala tadqiqotlari.

Annotation. Archaeological research involves many occupational hazards, including physical, biological, and climatic threats. The article aims to analyze the characteristics of labor protection in the field of archaeology, identify potential hazards, and develop recommendations for ensuring the safety of personnel on archaeological expeditions.

Key words. Labor protection, technical safety, production, archaeology, expedition, risk, field research.

Аннотация. Археологические исследования сопряжены с множеством профессиональных опасностей, включая физические, биологические и климатические. Целью статьи является анализ особенностей охраны труда в области археологии, выявление потенциальных опасностей и разработка рекомендаций по обеспечению безопасности персонала археологических экспедиций.

Ключевые слова. Охрана труда, техническая безопасность, производство, археология, экспедиция, риск, полевые исследования.

Introduction. Uzbekistan is like a huge open-air museum. Its invaluable historical exhibits, along with unique architectural ensembles located in Samarkand and Bukhara, Khiva and Shakhrisabz, Termez and Kokand, have been preserved in the vast expanses of ancient Khorezm, Karakalpakstan, Surkhandarya, Zarafshan and Fergana valleys, where the intercontinental trade caravan route connecting East and West passed. All this has been imprinted in the material culture and ethnic identity of the peoples of Uzbekistan. Every monument, settlement, or rock painting created by our ancestors and preserved

to this day is an important historical witness, that is, a document, and all of them await the discoverer of their mysterious world. Therefore, the first important issue on the agenda is the comprehensive preservation of the aforementioned monuments.

A professional archaeologist working in state scientific institutions of Uzbekistan has the right to conclude an international scientific contract and conduct archaeological research. These scientific institutions include research institutes within the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan dealing with historical problems (archaeology, art history), higher educational institutions with archaeology departments (NUUz, SamSU, KSU, TerSU), museums specializing in archaeology (Termez Archaeological Museum, Afrasiab Museum in Samarkand, Bukhara Regional Museum, Timurid State Museum, Museum of the History of the Peoples of Uzbekistan, and others).

Main Part. The life experience of humanity in the distant past confirms that any activity has potential danger. At the same time, it is possible to manage and reduce the level of risk in production conditions. But under no circumstances can absolute security be achieved.

Archaeology as a science often requires active fieldwork in conditions far from urban infrastructure. Archaeologists work in mountainous, desert, marsh, or forest zones, under the Influence of unfavorable climatic and natural factors. This necessitates the systematic organization of labor protection and compliance with safety regulations.

Physical risks constitute the main group of threats to the health and life of archaeologists during fieldwork. They are associated with the peculiarities of excavation work, the use of hand tools, work in difficult-to-access areas, and general physical exertion.

Working with a shovel, pickaxe, hoe, scraper, and hammer requires great attention and caution. Violation of safety regulations may result in:

- Cut and stabbed wounds,
- Injury and dislocation of joints,
- Head injury from careless shaking of a heavy instrument.

Archaeological activity, especially when working with ancient organic remains, in natural conditions and with insufficient sanitary infrastructure, can be accompanied by the influence of many biological factors. Ignoring these threats can lead to infectious diseases, intoxications, and epidemiological complications within the expedition.

In archaeology, biological safety is an important aspect of occupational safety, requiring the combination of medical training, sanitary discipline, and regular supervision. Ensuring basic sanitary conditions and competent prevention of infectious diseases contributes to the preservation of the health of expedition members and ensures the continuity of scientific work.

A comprehensive approach to occupational health and safety, including organizational, technical, sanitary, hygienic, and legal measures, is necessary to minimize occupational risks during archaeological research. These actions must be planned in advance and strictly followed throughout the entire expedition.

Systematic observance of these measures will allow not only to preserve the health of the participants of the archaeological expedition, but also to increase the effectiveness of scientific research through the stable and safe operation of the team.

Labor protection in archaeology is regulated by current labor and sanitary legislation, as well as industry standards aimed at ensuring the safety of working conditions in field scientific expeditions. Despite the peculiarities of archaeological work, expedition workers have the same labor rights and guarantees as workers in other fields, including the right to safe labor.

The main normative documents used in archaeological activity include:

- The Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan defines the employer's obligations to ensure safe working conditions, the mandatory provision of instructions, medical examinations, and personal protective equipment.
- The Law "On Labor Protection" enshrines the general principles of labor protection and the procedure for regulating safety relations between the employee and the employer.
- Sanitary Rules and Norms (SanPiN) – regulate the sanitary conditions of labor, including in field camps.
- GOSTs and departmental instructions on the safety of expeditionary and field work.

Legal aspects of labor protection in archaeology not only provide official protection for employees, but also create conditions for stable, responsible, and ethically sound scientific activity. Compliance with legislation is the key to preventing injuries, disputes, and disruptions in expeditionary work.

Archaeological activity is not only scientific research and work with cultural heritage, but also complex physical labor associated with many risks. The conditions of field expeditions, the remoteness of facilities, climatic and biological

threats, as well as the use of manual labor, require special attention to occupational safety and health issues.

Conclusion. Analysis shows that ensuring the safety of archaeologists is impossible without a comprehensive approach: from regulatory and legal regulation and instructions to sanitary and living conditions, medical observation, and the use of modern technologies. Expedition organizers are obliged to comply with all legal requirements, provide participants with the necessary protective equipment, and develop internal regulations, taking into account the specifics of the terrain.

Creating a safe working environment in archaeology is not only about caring for the lives and health of specialists, but also the basis for successful, continuous, and high-quality scientific research. Only with strict adherence to the principles of labor protection can the sustainable development of archaeological science and the preservation of its personnel potential be ensured.

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